

**Early walnut powder introduction for prevention of walnut sensitization in high-risk infants
with eczema.**

An open-label, randomized, non-inferiority trial

research plan

Abbreviated name: Walnut sensitization inhibition test

WISH-J Study

Walnut Intake for Suppression of High-Level Sensitization in Japan

Principal Investigator: Kiwako Yamamoto

**Physician, Department of Allergy, Allergy Center, National Center for Child Health and
Development**

〒2-10-1, Okura, Setagaya-ku, Tokyo 157-8535

Phone: 03-3416-0181

fax: 03-3415-9260

E-mail: yamamoto-k@ncchd.go.jp

Research Office Representative: Mayako Saito

**Physician, Department of Allergy, Allergy Center, National Center for Child Health and
Development**

〒2-10-1, Okura 2-chome, Setagaya-ku, Tokyo 157-8535

Phone: 03-3416-0611

fax: 03-3415-9260

E-mail: allergy_research@ncchd.go.jp

Establishment and Revision History

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1.1	2024/6/24.	Kiwako Yamamoto	Basis for setting the protein content of walnuts added in response to the technical expert's evaluation report.
1.2	2024/7/8	Kiwako Yamamoto	Paragraph 1.8 deleted in response to points raised by the Preliminary Examination Subcommittee.
1.3	27/7/2024	Kiwako Yamamoto	CRB Review Findings, Change description from 3 days per week to at least 3 days per week Change the way test meals are handed over. Possible disadvantages in the consent form added. 14. Corrected omission of research period January → November.
1.4	28/10/2024	Kiwako Yamamoto	Change in total quantity of walnut powder.
1.5	4/23/2025	Kiwako Yamamoto	Corrected discrepancies between research protocol and consent form

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mark	Unabbreviated expressions	
eCRF	Electronic Case Report Form	electronic case report form
EASI	The Eczema Area and Severity Index	
EDC	Electronic Data Capture	
FA	Food allergy	food allergy
IgE	Immunoglobulin E	
jRCT	Japan registry of clinical trials	Clinical Research Submission and Release System
OFCs	Oral Food Challenge	Oral food load test
POEM	The Patient-Oriented Eczema Measure	
TARC	Thymus and Activation-Regulated Chemokine	

Definition of a term

test intervention	Ingestion of the investigational food product (walnut powder).
study intervention period	From the start date of intake of the test food to the VISIT at 24 months of age (until the end date of intake)
Weeks of study intervention period	From the week of intake of the test food to the last week of the visit at 24 months of age. If the visit falls in the middle of the week, it must be the week prior to the Visit.
test (testing) period	From the date of registration to the date of the 24-month-old visit
X months old	Refers to the period from the date the subject reaches X months 0 days of age to the day before the (X + 1)-month birthday, based on the subject's date of birth.
legal representative	Spouse, person exercising parental authority, guardian, or other similar person of the subject of this study
Principal investigator	Principal investigators representing more than one site participating in the study
principal investigator	A physician who oversees the work related to the study at each site participating in the study
research physician	Physicians who will share clinical research duties under the guidance of the principal investigator at each site participating in the study
person who is being studied	Persons who are considered to be the main subject of the study based on eligibility criteria and other factors.
test subject	Persons who have obtained consent, meet eligibility criteria and are participating in the study
atopic dermatitis	The U.K. Working Party's diagnostic criteria for atopic dermatitis, developed by Williams et al. (Br J Dermatol 1994), require the presence of the major criterion and at least three minor criteria for diagnosis.
immediate allergy	Defined as the occurrence of any skin, respiratory, gastrointestinal, neurological, or circulatory symptoms included in the Sampson Severity Score (Table 2) within 120 minutes after ingestion of the suspected food, provided that other causes can be ruled out..
Maximum severity score	The maximum severity score refers to the highest Grade (1–5) assigned using the Sampson Severity Score during the study

	treatment period, as determined by the physician based on the subject's diary and caregiver's report.
Anaphylaxis	Anaphylaxis is defined as immediate allergic symptoms that are Grade 3 or higher on the Sampson severity score (Table 2).
contact dermatitis	Defined as skin symptoms around the mouth or in areas of direct contact within 15 minutes after ingestion of food.
Food protein-induced enterocolitis syndrome	Follows the diagnostic criteria of Novak et al.
IgE sensitization	An IgE sensitization is defined as a specific IgE antibody titer of 0.35 kUA/L or higher.
POEM Score	The Patient-Oriented Eczema Measure (POEM) consists of seven questions evaluating symptoms such as itching, dryness, redness, and sleep disturbance associated with atopic dermatitis. Parents or guardians complete the questionnaire weekly to assess disease severity. The POEM is recommended by the global Harmonising Outcome Measures for Eczema (HOME) initiative as a patient-reported outcome measure.
EASI Score	The Atopic Dermatitis Severity Scale was developed by Hanifin et al. The EASI score is calculated by a physician blinded to the site, extent, and severity of atopic dermatitis lesions (0-72). The global Harmonising Outcome Measures for Eczema (HOME) initiative recommends the use of the EASI score as an outcome measure for atopic dermatitis in clinical trials.

Table 1: The U.K. Working Party's diagnostic criteria (translated into Japanese by the Research Secretariat)

Atopic dermatitis is diagnosed when the major criterion (1) and three or more minor criteria (2) are met.

Main criterion
An itchy skin condition (or parental report of scratching or rubbing in a child)
Minor criteria
History of involvement of the skin creases such as folds of elbows, behind the knees, front of ankles or around the neck (including cheeks in children under 10).
A personal history of asthma or hay fever (or history of atopic disease in a first-degree relative in children under 4)
A personal history of a general dry skin in the last 12 months.
Visible flexural eczema (or eczema involving the cheeks/forehead and outer limbs in children under 4).
Onset under the age of 2 (not used if child is under 4).

Table 2: Sampson Classification

Grade	Skin	Gastrointestinal	Respiratory	Cardiovascular	Neurological
1	Itching, erythema, urticaria, vascular angioedema	Oral discomfort, mild nausea	Itchy throat, slight discomfort	–	–
2	Itching, erythema, urticaria,	Vomiting, 1–2 episodes of vomiting/diarrhea	Mild nasal congestion, runny nose,	–	Restlessness/anxiety

	vascular angioedema	, transient abdominal pain	1–2 sneezes, occasional cough		
3	Above symptoms	Repeated vomiting/diarrhea, persistent abdominal pain	Persistent nasal congestion, repeated sneezing, continuous coughing, wheezing	Tachycardia (HR \geq 15 bpm above normal)	Anxiety
4	Above symptoms	Above symptoms	Laryngeal stridor, barking cough, severe dyspnea, cyanosis, respiratory distress	Arrhythmia, hypotension	Agitation, sense of impending doom
5	Above symptoms	Above symptoms	Respiratory arrest	Severe hypotension, cardiac arrest	Loss of consciousness

1. Key contacts.

1.1. Principal investigator

Kiwako Yamamoto, Doctor, Department of General Allergy, Allergy Center, National Center for Child Health and Development

2-10-1, Okura, Setagaya-ku, Tokyo 157-8535, Japan

Tel: 03-3416-0181 (ext. 7910)

E-mail: yamamoto-k@ncchd.go.jp

1.2. Participating institutions and principal investigators

Kiwako Yamamoto, Doctor, Department of General Allergy, Allergy Center, National Center for Child Health and Development

Tsutomu Natsume, Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Hamamatsu University Hospital

Fumiya Yamade, Associate Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Narita Hospital, International University of Health and Welfare

Chikako Motomura, Medical Director, Department of Pediatrics, National Hospital Organization Fukuoka Hospital

Sayaka Hamaguchi, Doctor, Department of Pediatrics, Tokyo Metropolitan Hiroo Hospital

1.3. Research collaborator

See list of participating researchers

1.4. Research administration, coordination and management staff

Department of General Allergy, Allergy Center, National Center for Child Health and Development, Mayako Saito

2-10-1, Okura, Setagaya-ku, Tokyo 157-8535, Japan

Tel: 03-3416-0611 (ext. 7910)

E-mail: allergy_research@ncchd.go.jp

1.5. Statistician

Medical Support Center for the Japan Environment and Children's Study, National Center for Child Health and Development, Limin Yang (ext. 7877).

2-10-1, Okura, Setagaya-ku, Tokyo 157-8535, Japan

Tel: 03-3416-0181

1.6. Assignment and allocation

Medical Support Center for the Japan Environment and Children's Study, National Center for Child Health and Development, Limin Yang (ext. 7877)

2-10-1, Okura, Setagaya-ku, Tokyo 157-8535, Japan

Tel: 03-3416-0181

1.7. Data management

Allergy Center, National Center for Child Health and Development, Kumiko Watanabe

2-10-1, Okura, Setagaya-ku, Tokyo 157-8535, Japan

Tel: 03-3416-0181 (ext. 7661)

1.8. Monitoring

Head of Unit, Monitoring Unit, Data Science Division, Hospital Clinical Research Center, National Center for Child Health and Development, Mayumi Sako

2-10-1, Okura, Setagaya-ku, Tokyo 157-8535, Japan

Tel: 03-3416-0181 (ext. 7551)

1.9. Chief auditor

N/A

1.10. Walnut powder provider

B-Case Inc.

Representative director Tetsuaki Kon

3-2-1 Sakado, Takatsu-ku, Kawasaki, Kanagawa 213-0012, Japan

Tel: 03-5665-2311

2. Background and rationale.

2.1. Background

2.1.1 Prevention of food allergies through early intake

Food allergy is increasing worldwide, and once developed, requires dietary restrictions until remission, which has a significant impact on the lives of the individual and their caregivers. In recent years, the dual-allergen-exposure hypothesis has been proposed as the mechanism of food allergy development.¹⁾ This hypothesis suggests that in patients with atopic dermatitis, early exposure to allergens through the gut (via eating) promotes immune tolerance, while initial exposure through the skin leads to allergic sensitization. Based on this hypothesis, it has been suggested that preventing percutaneous sensitization by maintaining healthy skin during infancy and inducing immune tolerance through ingestion of food antigen proteins from an early age may have a preventive effect against food allergy development. In fact, as an oral intervention, recent data from randomized controlled studies have shown that the onset of allergy can be prevented by early initiation of oral intake of foods in infancy, such as hen eggs²⁾, peanuts³⁾, and milk⁴⁾. Interventions in which multiple foods are consumed simultaneously have also been reported⁶⁾ (Table 1).

Table 1: Randomized controlled trials of food allergy prevention by early intake

food	target group	Presence or absence of eczema in the subject	Intervention details (Protein content)	Intervention period	outcome	Prevalence of both groups Placebo group vs. intervention group		Country/Region/Year
						ITT	PPS	
hens egg	High-risk infant (Family history)	± (Proactive treatment)	Heated whole egg powder (25 mg → 125 mg/day)	From 6 months to 12 months of age	Chicken egg allergy at 12 months of age	38% vs. 8%. (p=0.0001)	38% vs. 4% (p<0.0001)	2017, Japan ²⁾
peanuts	Infants with severe AD, EA or both	±	Snacks with peanuts or butter (6g/week)	From 4-10 months old to 60 months old	Peanut allergy at 60 months of age	17.2% vs. 3.2 (p<0.001)	17.3% vs. 0.3 (p<0.001)	.2015, United Kingdom ³⁾
(cow's) milk	General infant	± (Proactive treatment)	Milk powder ≥ 10ml/day (150 mg/day)	From 1 month to 3 months of age	Cow's milk allergy at 6 months	6.8% vs. 0.8 (p<0.001)	8.7% vs. 0.0 (p<0.001)	.2021, Japan ⁴⁾

					s of age			
6 kinds of food* ₁	breast-fed child	±	2g/day x 2 times/week	From 3 to 6 months of age	At least one or more FAs aged 1-3 years	7.1% vs. 5.6% (P = 0.32)	7.3% vs 2.4% (p=0.01)	2016, United Kingdom ⁵⁾
6 kinds of food* ₂	Infants with AD	+	6 mixed powder MP (each with different protein content, 3 levels of MP1, 2, 3) (* ₃)	From 3-4 months of age for a total of 12 weeks	FA at 18 months of age	23.8% vs. 8.4% (p=0.066)	24.1% vs. 8.5% (P=.0065)	2022, Japan ⁶⁾

1: Hens eggs, milk, wheat, peanuts, fish, sesame seeds

*2: Hens eggs, milk, wheat, soybeans, buckwheat, peanuts

*3: Content of each food (mg)/protein (mg)

	MP1	MP2	MP3
hens egg	2.5 (2.2)	7.5 (6.6)	20 (17.6)
(cow's) milk	2.5 (0.3)	7.5 (0.9)	20 (2.4)
Wheat	2.5 (0.2)	7.5 (0.6)	20 (1.6)
soya bean (soybean)	2.5 (0.9)	7.5 (2.7)	20 (7.2)
Close	2.5 (0.3)	7.5 (0.9)	20 (2.4)
Peanuts	2.5 (0.6)	7.5 (1.8)	20 (4.8)

2.1.2 Rapid increase in nut allergies and existence of walnut protein in the environment

Meanwhile, according to the Consumer Affairs Agency's nationwide survey on health hazards due to immediate-type food allergies, increased consumption of nuts has led to a rapid increase of nut allergies in Japan since 2014 (Figure 1). Currently, nuts are the leading cause of immediate-type allergies in children aged 3-5 years, surpassing hen's eggs and cow's milk (Table 2), with walnuts being the most common among nuts. In June 2020, the Consumer Affairs Agency announced its intention to add walnuts, currently a recommended allergen labelling item, to the list of mandatory allergen labelling items. Like hens' egg, there is an urgent need to establish preventive measures against nut allergies.

Figure 1: Percentage of cases of the top causes of immediate type allergy
Excerpt from "National Survey on Health Damage Caused by Immediate Type Food Allergy,"
Consumer Affairs Agency

Rank	Age 0 (1,876 cases)	Age 1–2 (1,435 cases)	Age 3–6 (1,525 cases)	Age 7–17 (906 cases)	Age ≥18 (338 cases)
1	Egg 60.6%	Egg 36.3%	Tree nuts 27.8%	Cow’s milk 16.9%	Wheat 22.5%
2	Cow’s milk 24.8%	Cow’s milk 17.6%	Cow’s milk 16.0%	Tree nuts 16.8%	Shellfish 16.9%
3	Wheat 10.8%	Tree nuts 15.4%	Egg 14.7%	Egg 14.5%	Fruits 9.8%
4		Fish egg 8.2%	Peanut 12.0%	Shellfish 10.2%	Fish 7.7%
5		Fish egg 10.3%	Fish egg 10.3%	Peanut 9.1%	Tree nuts 5.9%
6		Wheat 5.8%	Wheat 6.7%	Fruits 7.8%	Cow’s milk 5.0%
7				Wheat 7.6%	

Table 2: Causal Foods by Age Group

Excerpt from "National Survey on Health Damage Caused by Immediate Type Food Allergy," Consumer Affairs Agency

A study of 45 Japanese households in 2020⁷⁾ found that the group with higher family consumption of walnuts tended to have higher concentrations of walnut protein in the dust of their homes. On the other hand, walnut protein was also detected in dust from homes where walnuts were not consumed (5/22 cases), suggesting that, from the perspective of transdermal sensitization, there is a need for early consumption in high-risk children, regardless of whether or not they consume walnuts at home.

2.1.3 Challenges in early walnut introduction

The American dietary guideline⁸⁾ recommend the introduction of hen eggs and peanuts at 6-12 months for allergy prevention. On the other hand, while there is no evidence that removing other foods, including nuts, until 12 months prevents allergies, they similarly recommend introducing nuts, including walnuts, at 6-12 months. Other countries, including Japan, do not include early introduction of nuts in their guidelines.

When introducing nuts during weaning or early childhood, feasibility and safety must also be considered. Nuts pose a risk of choking and aspiration due to their morphological characteristics,

and the Japanese Pediatric Society as well as the Consumer Affairs Agency recommend that they should not be consumed under the age of five. In the past, there was a report from one pediatric tertiary emergency hospital in Australia⁹⁾ that the number of choking cases increased after publication of study on the preventive effect of early peanut consumption (LEAPstudy)³⁾. In view of safety considerations, we recommend early intake of nuts during weaning or early childhood by powder or low-viscosity pastes. A retrospective chart review of infants who received such recommendation showed that while over 90% of children were able to consume hen's eggs by 12 months of age, only 30% were able to consume walnuts. Although there were no safety issues concerning consumption when walnut was prepared in an ingestible form for infants, the need to improve feasibility at home was suggested (Nutrients, 2024 accepted).

As an intervention study for early introduction of allergens including walnuts, there is a randomized non-blinded intervention trial examining the safety and feasibility of early introduction using a mixed powder of 10 allergens (30 mg, 90 mg and 300 mg of each food protein) (n=45).^{10) 11)} All consumed safely and none had any serious adverse events after 2-12 months of induction. Additionally, in Australia, a randomized controlled trial comparing the presence or absence of nut allergy at 18 months of age is currently underway.¹²⁾ This trial focuses on children with peanut allergy (4-11 months of age), who are at high risk of nut allergy. Trial compares two groups, group starting consumption of nuts at home after negative oral food challenge (OFC) and group starting consumption of nuts at home from the beginning.

In addition to the optimal form of intake and method of introduction, the timing of initiation should be considered for the early intake of nuts. Compared to hens' egg and peanuts, the sensitization rate for nuts in infants are low, increase with age, and vary by region^{13) 14) 15) 16) 17)} (Table 3).

Table 3: Walnut sensitization in infants according to previous reports

target group	Definition of sensitization	Sensitization Ratio	Country/Region/Year
General group, 1 year old n=1218	SPT and IgE	Walnuts 0%. Fifteen (1.2%) were sensitized to peanuts or nuts (1 hazel, 1 cashew, 13 peanut).	Spain 1996 ¹³⁾
child with AD (i.e. someone with ADHD) n=18	IgE	Walnuts 0%. No sensitization of nuts under 5 years of age	India 2008 ¹⁴⁾
All patients suspected of having FA and referred to a specialized institution under 2 years of age	IgE (cutoff 0.1, 0.35, 0.7)	Walnuts 0%. (25% hazel, 0% almond)	Mexico City 2020 ¹⁵⁾
AD Child n=90 2-48 months old	IgE (≥ 0.35)	Nuts (hazelnuts, almonds, walnuts) 17.7% (peanuts 8%)	Iran 2012 ¹⁶⁾
AD children n=912 Under 2 years old	IgE (≥ 0.35)	Walnuts 8.7% (hazelnuts 14.0%, cashews 8.0%, almonds 3.8%, eggs 49.7%, peanuts 6.8%)	Turkey 2020 ¹⁷⁾

Since no data on walnut sensitization in high risk of FA children or the general population during infancy in Japan was available, we conducted a retrospective review of chart data at the National Center for Child Health and Development (NCCHD). Among tests performed in children under 2 years with atopic dermatitis (n=32,912), while hen's egg often showed increases from 3-6 months of age, the positive rates for walnut and Jug r 1 specific IgE tests were lower than hen's eggs, and sensitization began later, around 15-18 months (Hamaguchi et al. CEA 2024).

Therefore, introduction of hen's egg from six months (recommendation based on evidence from the PETIT study²⁾), may not apply to nuts. At present, this point has not been examined in prospective studies. In early weaning, there are many foods that should be introduced for the first time, including hen's eggs, and if early intake of nuts is required as well, the burden on caregivers will be high.

Regarding the measurement of specific IgE antibodies related to walnut allergy, it has been reported that Jugr1 is the major component allergen in walnut allergy patients and has been reported to have much superior diagnostic ability compared to crude walnut antigen IgE measurements.¹⁸⁾

Based on these facts, we considered it necessary to establish a prevention method with high feasibility and safety for walnut allergy, which is increasing in Japan. In order to establish this, we designed a randomized open-labelled intervention trial using walnut powder to investigate the non-inferiority of the preventive effect on the onset of walnut allergy regardless of whether walnut consumption was started before or after completion of weaning.

2.2. Overview of medicinal products, etc.

The walnut used in this study is a commercially available food, but because the study will test non-inferiority of efficacy with regard to suppressing specific IgE sensitization related to walnut allergy, the clinical study will be conducted as a specified clinical trial in accordance with unapproved medical product.

Walnut powder

Manufacturing method: Heating (85°C for 10 minutes), freeze-drying, grinding.

Ingredients:

Walnut powder (containing 2.5 mg of walnut protein) 1 packet (0.8 g) contains 2.5 mg of walnut protein, equivalent to 0.017 g walnut.

Walnut powder (containing 7.5 mg of walnut protein) 1 packet (0.8 g) contains 7.5 mg of walnut protein, equivalent to 0.051 g walnut.

Walnut powder (containing 20 mg of walnut protein) 1 packet (2.2 g) contains 20 mg of walnut protein, equivalent to 0.137 g walnut.

Additives (common to all formulations): Modified starch, fructooligosaccharide, dextrin, starch, antioxidant (Vitamin C).

Walnut production area: United States of America

Manufacturing: Ikeda Tohka Industries Co.,Ltd. / Hatsuratsu Co.,Ltd. / B-Case Co.,Ltd.

Packaging: TOSHO EXCEL Co.,Ltd.

Shelf-life from manufacturing: 6 months at room temperature after sealed individual packaging.*

Microbiological standards: Total viable count: $\leq 10,000/g$, coliform bacteria negative, Staphylococcus aureus negative

Contamination: Confirmed absence of contamination with eggs, milk, wheat, shrimp/crab, buckwheat, and peanuts using the following measurement kits during manufacturing.

[Eggs, wheat, peanuts, buckwheat, milk, walnuts] Screening test using Nippon Ham Co., Ltd. FASTKIT ELISA Ver.III series

[Crustaceans] Screening test using Nissui Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd. FA Test EIA-Crustaceans II "Nissui"

*The shelf life stated is the longest period confirmed at the time of writing this research protocol and is expected to extend to a maximum of 2 years as verification progresses. Specific expiration dates will be printed on the outer packaging when distributed to subjects.

3. Objectives.

To examine the walnut sensitization suppression effects of two different walnut introduction timings (6-8 months and 12-14 months of age) in high-risk infants for food allergy development through a randomized open-label non-inferiority trial.

The primary evaluation endpoint is the proportion of Jug r 1 specific IgE sensitization ($\geq 0.35\text{IU}$) by ImmunoCAP method at 24 months of age.

3.1. Trial Phase

Trial aims to demonstrate the non-inferiority of the intervention and corresponds to a Phase III trial.

3.2. Sample size

The proportion of children with atopic dermatitis with Jugr1 sensitization at 21-24 months of age was 21% according to Hamaguchi et al (Clin Exp Allergy. 2024). There are no intervention studies investigating Jugr1 sensitization at 24 months of age after intake of walnuts from early weaning period. We estimated from data of multi-allergen powder⁶⁾ and hens' egg prevention studies²⁾ that suppression of food allergy onset by early intake would be 60.5-80% and that Jugr1 sensitization would also be suppressed in the same context. This gives us an estimation of Jugr1 sensitization rate at 5%. In addition, if the sensitization rate was considered to be non-inferior when intake of walnuts was from the post weaning period (12-15 months of age), in order to consider the non-inferiority, a non-inferiority margin of 10%, statistical power 80% and the significance level of 2.5% in each tail, 99 subjects in both groups would be required. Taking into account a drop-out rate of 10%, a total of 220 subjects, 110 subjects in each group (Group A: walnut intake from early weaning period, Group B: walnut intake from post weaning period) are planned to be enrolled.

The NCCHD Allergy Center has over 120 initial visits to the infant allergy clinic annually, with about 30% being infants of eligible age for trial registration, plus many eligible infants being followed in research outpatient clinic, resulting in an expected annual registration of over 60 patients. The number of patients expected to be registered per year from the other 4 participating institutes are around 100. Together, the 5 facilities are expected to register about 160 patients annually, making recruitment feasible within the registration period.

3.3. Study design

This is an open-labelled randomized controlled trial to demonstrate the non-inferiority of the preventive effect on the onset of walnut allergy regardless of whether walnut consumption was started before (Group A: 6-8 months of age) or after completion of weaning (Group B: 12-14 months of age).

The flow of the study is shown in the diagram below.

[Rationale] For hen's eggs²⁾, peanuts³⁾, and milk⁴⁾, the allergy prevention effects of early

introduction during infancy have already been demonstrated in randomized controlled trials, and prevention effects have been reported in multi-allergen intervention studies⁵⁾⁶⁾ (although walnuts were not included), suggesting that early introduction can be expected to have allergy prevention effects for any food. American dietary guidelines⁸⁾ recommend nut consumption during weaning. In our clinical practice, we also recommend early introduction of nuts in powder or paste form. Therefore, setting a placebo group without consumption would not align with current practices. However, since nuts including walnuts do not have a tradition of early introduction during infancy, far fewer families can actually start early introduction in clinical practice compared to hen's eggs (Nutrients, 2024, accepted). Additionally, walnuts tend to be sensitized later than hen's eggs (Clin Exp Allergy, 2024, accepted). Considering these circumstances, we set up a non-inferiority trial comparing sensitization suppression effects by introduction timing, randomizing subjects to groups before or after weaning completion.

Group B (walnut introduction after weaning completion) in this trial will completely avoid walnuts until a maximum of 14 months of age, but considering Japan's infant walnut consumption patterns and the suggested later onset of sensitization, this is considered within an acceptable range.

Criteria for subject selection, exclusion, and study discontinuation

Subjects meeting the inclusion criteria and do not conflict with all of the exclusion criteria will be enrolled in this study.

3.4. Subject inclusion criteria.

1. Children aged 5-7 months at the time of consent.
2. Children diagnosed, or judged to have developed atopic dermatitis before 6 months of age using the UK Working Party diagnostic criteria at the time of consent (including children who have already started treatment and are in remission).
3. Children whose legal representatives have provided written informed consent after receiving explanation and achieving sufficient understanding of study participation.

[Rationale] 1), 2) Because this study aims to demonstrate non-inferiority of the efficacy of intervention from early or complete weaning for infants at high risk of developing food allergies.

3.5. Exclusion criteria

1. Children born at less than 37 weeks of gestational age.
2. Children with previous experience consuming walnuts or walnut products.
3. Children with suspected or pre-existing food protein-induced gastroenteropathy
4. Children suffering from illnesses that may interfere with the study (e.g. an underlying illness that requires tube feeding or an underlying illness that is likely to result in prolonged hospitalization during the study period for treatment or surgery).
5. Children whose legal representatives are unable to communicate adequately in Japanese
6. Children deemed ineligible by the principal investigator, sub-principal investigator or co-investigator.

[Rationale] 1)-4) Due to concerns about the impact on efficacy evaluation; 4)-6) Due to concerns about the impact on safety or ethical considerations.

3.6. Study intervention discontinuation and participant discontinuation/withdrawal.

The principal investigator or co-investigator will discontinue the study food intake if he/she decides that the study cannot be continued for any of the following reasons. The date and reason for discontinuation will be recorded in medical records and electronic case report form (eCRF), and any necessary tests will be conducted at discontinuation to assess efficacy and safety (if discontinuation occurs prior to study intervention, efficacy and safety will not be assessed). If discontinuation is due to illness, follow-up will continue as far as possible until the subject's recovery.

- 1) Inability to start the study intervention within the specified period for the assigned group.

- 2) Positive result in OFC of the test food conducted during the study intervention period.
- 3) Difficulty continuing study intervention due to adverse events during study intervention period.
- 4) Withdrawal of consent by the subject's legal representative.
- 5) Discovery after registration that inclusion criteria are not met or that exclusion criteria are violated.
- 6) Difficulty continuing the study due to illness or other medical condition.
- 7) Subject does not visit due to relocation or other reasons.
- 8) Other situations where study discontinuation is deemed appropriate by the principal investigator, sub-principal investigator or co-investigator.
- 9)

3.7. Study discontinuation criteria.

The principal investigator will consider whether or not to continue the study if any of the following apply. If the efficacy and safety evaluation committee or the certified clinical research review committee recommends or instructs discontinuation, the study will be discontinued. Within 10 days of deciding early study termination, the principal investigator will submit a discontinuation notice to the certified clinical research review committee and submit a specified clinical research discontinuation report to the Minister of Health, Labor and Welfare. The administrator of the implementing medical institution will be promptly notified in document with the reason for the discontinuation, and subjects' legal representatives will be promptly notified with appropriate post-processing guaranteed.

- 1) Obtaining significant information on the quality, safety or efficacy of the test food.
- 2) Difficulty recruiting research subjects or high dropout rates making study completion difficult.
- 3) Instructions for study protocol changes from the efficacy and safety evaluation committee or certified clinical research review committee that are deemed difficult to accept.

4. Matters relating to the treatment of clinical research subjects.

4.1. Subject registration procedures

This study uses an Electronic Data Capture system (EDC) for subject registration and randomized allocation (NCCHD REDCap system).

- 1) The principal investigator or co-investigator obtain written consent from legal representatives (parents) using designated forms and confirm all inclusion criteria are met and no exclusion criteria are violated.
- 2) The principal investigator or co-investigator enter subject registration information (yes/no for each inclusion criterion, yes/no for each exclusion criterion) into EDC for eligible candidates. A subject identification number is assigned and an allocation to one of two groups occurs.
- 3) Once registered, the NCCHD REDCap system sends a email confirmation notifications to the research office, principal investigator, sub-principal investigator, co-investigators and the monitoring personnel.
- 4) The principal investigator or co-investigator confirms the allocation results and informs the subjects of visit 2 (start of the study intervention) timing.

[Registration notes].

- 1) Ineligible subjects and those who withdraw consent before registration are not entered into NCCHD REDCap.
- 2) Registration is complete upon receiving the confirmation email notification.
- 3) Promptly contact the research office for erroneous registration, duplicate registration, consent withdrawal, discontinuation or dropout.
- 4) For duplicate registrations, the first registration takes priority.

4.2. Allocation method and adjustment factors

Subjects are allocated 1:1 to the early weaning walnut initiation group (group A) and the weaning completion walnut initiation group (group B) using permuted block randomization in registration order. No adjustment factors are used.

4.3. Blinding.

The study interventions in this study will not be blinded to the subjects, principal investigator, sub-principal investigator and co-investigators.

4.4. Emergency unblinding.

Not applicable to this study.

4.5. Study intervention

The study intervention in this study is the consumption of test food.

The principal investigator or co-investigator instructs the legal representatives (parents) or caregivers on how to consume the test food and how to record the diaries at the time of registration. The test food will be distributed to the legal representatives or caregivers and OFC will be conducted at each facility's outpatient clinic for safety reasons at the start of intake (visit 2) and at the time of increased intake (visit 3, visit 4). In both groups, an OFC assessment of daily walnut intake (4 g in total) will also be conducted at visit 6 for those who wish. Details of these OFCs will follow a separate instruction manual.

Investigators check diary consumption records at each visit. When test food is given to children, consumption is considered to have occurred if more than one mouthful is swallowed (explain to legal representatives to mix with amounts the subject can finish eating). If vomiting or spitting up occurs after test food consumption, re-administration on the same day is not performed regardless of time from consumption to vomiting (follow the response flow for allergic symptom onset after investigational food consumption [Appendix 1]). However, during initial or dose escalation OFC at outpatient clinics, re-administration may occur at investigator's discretion.

Study intervention periods are as follows. For early weaning walnut initiation group (Group A): study intervention starts between 6-8 months of age until visit 6 at 24 months or discontinuation date. For weaning completion walnut initiation group (Group B): study intervention starts between 12-14 months of age until visit 6 at 24 months or discontinuation date. For those who wish to undergo daily walnut consumption OFC at visit 6, study intervention ends upon OFC completion for both groups.

[Walnut intake capacity, method and duration]

① Early weaning walnut initiation group (group A)

<Visit dates for walnut powder initiation and dose escalation>

Visit 2: When subject is 6-8 months old and within 6 weeks of visit 1

Visit 3: Visit 2 date + 8 weeks (± 2 weeks)

Visit 4: Visit 2 date + 16 weeks (± 2 weeks)

- Step 1: From the start of visit 2 intervention until the day before visit 3, 1 packet (0.8 g) of walnut powder (containing 2.5 mg of walnut protein)/dose
- Step 2: From the day of visit 3 to the day before visit 4, 1 packet (0.8 g) of walnut powder (containing 7.5 mg of walnut protein) /dose
- Step 3: From the day of visit 4 to the day of visit 6, 1 packet (2.2 g) of walnut powder (containing 20 mg of walnut protein)/dose

Consume once a day, 3-7 days per week.

[Rationale].

Regarding the safety and feasibility of the amount of walnut protein in test food, there is a pilot study using mixed powder of 10 allergens including walnuts (30mg, 90mg, 300mg of each food protein) for early introduction (n=45)^{10,11}. All subjects were able to consume safely with no serious adverse events after 2-12 months of introduction. Therefore, we considered up to a maximum 300 mg protein dose to be safely consumable. For food allergy prevention effects,

while there are no walnut intervention studies, we referred to hen's egg allergy prevention studies²⁾ (protein amount 25mg→125mg in 2 stages) and other multi-allergen intervention studies⁶⁾ (hen's egg protein 2.2mg→6.6mg→17.6mg, peanut protein 0.6mg→1.8mg→4.8mg), and evidence from clinical practice showing minimal oral consumption can be effective for immune induction¹⁹⁾. The amount of walnut proteins were set at 2.5mg, 7.5mg, 20mg in 3 stages based on allergy expert opinions and manufacturing capabilities of nut powder companies, as well as taking into consideration the safety and minimal effective amounts (equivalent to approximately 0.017g, 0.051g, 0.137g walnut respectively, assuming 146mg protein per 1g walnut). The frequency of 3 or more times per week was set considering that peanut prevention intervention studies³⁾ and 6-allergen prevention intervention studies⁵⁾ showed sufficient prevention effects with 2-3 times per week consumption when adherence was good, while also considering caregiver burden for interventions lasting up to 1.5 years.

[Common items for both groups]

- Consumption method: The test food is taken once a day. The intake should be mixed with other foods such as porridge. To prevent consumption residue, explain to legal representatives to mix with amounts the subject can finish eating.
- Subjects must not consume walnuts or products containing walnuts, other than the test foods and the OFC in this study, from the time of obtaining study consent until the end or discontinuation of the study intervention. However, for breastfeeding mothers, there is no need to avoid remove walnuts or products containing walnuts.
- Acceptable consumption frequency: At least 3 days per week.
- Interruption of consumption during illness: Test food should not be consumed during illnesses such as gastroenteritis, fever, etc. Interruption of consumption of the test food due to temporary illness with the expectation of resuming normal consumption does not fall under criterion 3 for discontinuation of the study. After symptom improvement, consumption should be resumed at the same amount of walnut powder that was consumed before the temporary interruption.
- Test foods are distributed in outpatient clinics and delivered by the respective medical institution as appropriate for cases where it is difficult or unnecessary to see the patient in the step 3 period.
- In case of allergic symptoms due to consumption of test food.

If allergic symptoms are suspected due to consumption of test food, legal representatives or caregivers should temporarily stop consumption, follow the response flow for allergic symptom onset (Appendix 1), and contact the consultation service at the respective medical facility. The principal investigator or co-investigator receiving the contact will determine if emergency visits are necessary. However, when contact dermatitis suspected symptoms appear after consumption of the test food, the test food should be applied to the lips and around the mouth before consumption for prevention, and retry consumption again the next day. If symptoms do not appear, continue consumption. If symptoms persist, temporarily stop consumption and contact the consultation service at the respective medical facility, as in the case of other symptoms.

- Antihistamines and white petrolatum will be prescribed at the time of registration and, if necessary, will be used in accordance with the flow in the event of allergic symptoms (Appendix 1), or under the instruction of the principal investigator, co-investigator.
- Treatment of atopic dermatitis will be provided within the scope of insurance coverage for routine care at each facility.

4.6. Observations/test items and treatment information to be reported

The principal investigator, co-investigator will conduct observations, tests and evaluations according to the time schedule and collect data in an electronic case report form (eCRF). If the study intervention is discontinued, data will be collected at that point for the end-of-study (at 24 months of age) endpoints. If the intervention is discontinued due to illness, follow-up continues as far as possible until the subject recovers to its normal status.

<Schedule Table>.

		duration of the intervention (e.g. in a clinical trial)					At the end or discontinuation of the study intervention
Visit	1	2	3	4	5	temporarily medical examination	6
Setting period (Group A)	5-7 months old	At 6-8 months of age and within 6 weeks of visit 1	+8 +/- 2 weeks after Visit2	+16 +/- 2 weeks after Visit 2	At 12-14 months of age		At 24 months of age (± 4 weeks) or date of discontinuation
Setting period (Group B)		At 12-14 months of age	+8 +/- 2 weeks after Visit2	+16 +/- 2 weeks after Visit 2	+24 +/- 2 weeks after Visit 2		At 24 months of age (± 4 weeks) or date of discontinuation
Obtaining Consent	○						
Registration and allocation ¹⁾	○						
Age of onset of atopic dermatitis ²⁾	○						
Background and living environment of subjects and blood	○						

relatives ³							
Walnut intake in the surrounding area ⁴⁾	○	○ (Group B only)			○ (Group A only)		○
Nutritional intake status ⁵⁾		○					○
Complications/History	○	○					
OFC at the implementing medical facility ⁶⁾		○ Test food start OFC	○ Test food bulking OFC	○ test food Increased OFC		○ (Temporary OFC)	○ (daily intake of walnuts OFC: on request)
Ingestion of test food		Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 3		Step 3
Height and Weight	○	○	○	○	○		○
EASI Score ^(7) 0)	○	○	○	○	○		○
POEM score ^(8) 0)	○	○	○	○	○		○
Caregiver Burden Level on Test Intervention ^(9) 0)			○	○	○		○
History of immediate walnut allergy ^(10) 0)		○	○	○	○	○	○
History of food protein-induced gastroenteropathy ^(1) 1) 0)		○	○	○	○	○	○

Presence of expirator y wheezing (1) (2) (0)							<input type="radio"/>
Allergic rhinitis (1) (3) (0)							<input type="radio"/>
Presence of immediate food allergies other than walnuts (1) (4) (0)							<input type="radio"/>
Blood test (1) (5) (0)	<input type="radio"/>	(Group B only) <input type="radio"/>			(Group A only) 0		<input type="radio"/>
Check logbooks (1) (6) (0)			<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>		<input type="radio"/>
adverse event		<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

<Detail of survey items>.

Collected information is entered into eCRF as data for the study.

- 1) Registration/allocation: Date of consent, date of birth and eligibility information registered in NCCHD REDCap system for allocation.
- 2) Atopic dermatitis onset age: Age at diagnosis based on UKWP criteria, collected through medical history-taking.
- 3) Subject and family background: From medical records and questionnaires.
 Subject background: gender, age (months) at registration → From medical records.
 Gestational weeks, birth height, birth weight, mode of delivery (vaginal delivery/cesarean section), race → From questionnaires.
 Subject's maternal background: History of allergic diseases → From questionnaires.
 Subject's paternal background: History of allergic diseases → From questionnaires.
 Background of subjects' siblings: number of siblings, age, sex of siblings, history of allergic diseases → From questionnaires
 Pets (dogs, cats, other) within the residence, smoking by family members → From questionnaires
- 4) Surrounding walnut consumption status: From questionnaires
 - Frequency and quantity of walnut intake of family members living together
 - Household situation of paternal and maternal parents
 - Frequency of visits
 - Frequency and quantity of walnut intake
- 5) Nutritional intake status: From nutritional record forms.
 - Intake of breast milk, general milk, allergy milk

- Weaning or not and start date
 - Intake of following foods (and if so, its' starting date)
 - walnut foods (other than the test food)/eggs/milk (dairy products other than milk powder)/wheat/soy/peanut/cash/ hazel/almond products
- 6) OFC at the participating institute:
- (1) Test food initiation OFC (visit 2) and dose escalation OFC (visits 3 and 4): 1 packet of walnut powder (containing 2.5 mg of walnut protein) in visit 2, 1 packet of walnut powder (containing 7.5 mg of walnut protein) in visit 3 and 1 packet of walnut powder (containing 20 mg of walnut protein) in visit 4, each in the form of a single loading dose.
 - (2) Emergency OFC: When allergic symptoms are suspected during home consumption and principal investigator or co-investigator decides that it's necessary on emergency visit, single-dose challenge will be conducted with 1 packet of walnut powder (dose at the step level when symptoms occurred).
 - (3) Daily walnut intake OFC (visit 6): For volunteers at visit 6, 40-minute divided-dose OFC with walnut equivalent to 1 walnut (4g) (dose divided into 1g-3g)
- For OFC(1)-(3), the decision is made according to the PRACTALL criteria given in Table 3.²⁰⁾ and is considered positive if any of the following criteria (1) to (3) are met within 120 minutes of the last intake of the food.
- ① One [A] symptom category shown in Table 3
 - ② Three [B] symptom categories shown in Table 3
 - ③ One [B] symptom category shown in Table 3 persists
- The principal investigator or co-investigator collects from the electronic medical record the date of OFC, time of intake, highest score for each category by site, overall decision time, test result, basis for decision, and persistent symptoms if one [B] symptom category persists.
- 7) EASI (Eczema Area and Severity Index) score: The principal investigator or co-investigator determines the location, extent and severity of atopic dermatitis, calculates the EASI score and collects each assessment score from the electronic medical record.
 - 8) POEM (Patient Oriented Eczema Measure) score: POEM consists of seven questions assessing skin dryness, redness sleep disturbance, etc. due to atopic dermatitis. Information is collected from questionnaires answered by legal representatives or caregivers.
 - 9) Level of burden on caregivers with regard to the study intervention: The principal investigator or co-investigator conduct multiple-choice questioning(very much/quite a lot/slightly/not at all) at each visit to collect information.
 - 10) Immediate-type walnut allergy history: Principal investigator/co-investigators collect presence/absence of symptoms and maximum severity scores using Sampson classification during the period from previous visit to current visit through history-taking, diary confirmation, and emergency visits for investigational food consumption when necessary.
 - 11) History of food protein-induced enterocolitis syndrome: Principal investigator/co-investigators collect through history-taking whether Acute FPIES, Chronic FPIES, FPE, FPIAP, or "other" not fitting any category occurred during the period from previous visit to current visit, with "yes/no" responses, and for "yes" cases: "diagnosis/suspected," presence/absence of each diagnostic definition item, and suspected foods (multiple selections possible) from electronic medical records (see Appendix 2 for definitions).
 - 12) Presence or absence of expiratory wheezing: Principal investigator/co-investigators collect through history-taking the presence/absence of occurrence during the study intervention period.
 - 13) Presence or absence of allergic rhinitis: Principal investigator/co-investigators will collect information through history-taking the presence/absence of the condition diagnosed during the study intervention period.

- 14) Presence or absence of immediate-type food allergy other than walnuts: Principal investigator/co-investigators collect through history-taking the presence/absence of disease names and causative foods.
- 15) Blood tests: Collect 3ml whole blood to measure total IgE antibody levels, specific IgE antibody levels (walnut, Jug r 1), and serum TARC values. Total IgE and specific IgE antibody levels are measured by ImmunoCAP method. Principal investigator/co-investigators collect results from electronic medical records.
- 16) Diary records 4 weeks per page, with legal representatives or caregivers recording: presence/absence of allergic symptoms (perioral symptoms, systemic symptoms), other food consumption status during symptomatic periods, test food consumption status (presence/absence of consumption, reasons for inability to consume 3+ times per week [multiple choice: ①forgot consumption, ②child's refusal, ③other (free text)]). For systemic symptoms, complete systemic symptom onset records (see Appendix: Diary). Principal investigator/co-investigators collect completed diary pages (4-week intervals) at relevant visits and record: presence/absence of diary confirmation, diary confirmation date, collection period (weeks) for recovered diary pages, total weeks achieving 3+ times per week consumption within collection period.

Table 3 PRACTALL criteria

I. Skin Skin Skin	<p>A. Erythematous rash: % area involved (see body surface area diagram) Erythematous rash: % area involved (see body surface area diagram) 0 = Absent / None 1 = Mild few areas of faint erythema / 1-3 locations, 5-10% as : 2 = Moderate areas of erythema / 10%<, ≤50 3 = Severe generalized marked erythema / >50 Figure Law of 5</p>	
	<p>B. Pruritus pruritus</p> <p>0= Absent / None 1= Mild, occasional scratching 2= Moderate: scratching continuously for >2 minutes at a time 3= Severe: hard continuous scratching - excoriations / Severe: hard continuous scratching, epidermal excoriations [B].</p> <p>0= Absent / None</p> <p>1= Mild: less than 3 hives, or mild lip edema / Mild: less than 3 hives, or mild lip swelling [B]</p> <p>C. Urticaria / angioedema Urticaria: Angioedema</p> <p>2= Moderate: more than 3 and less than 10 hives, or significant lip or face edema / Moderate: more than 3 and less than 10 hives, or significant lip or face swelling [A].</p> <p>3= Severe: generalized involvement / Severe: generalized [A].</p>	

II. Upper respiratory Upper respiratory tract	D. Rash rash	0= Absent / None	
		1= Mild: few areas of faint erythema / Mild: small areas of faint erythema	
		2= Moderate: areas of erythema/ Moderate: erythema present [B].	
		3= Severe: generalized marked erythema (>50%)/ Severe: erythema more extensive than 50% [A].	
	A. Sneezing/ Itching Sneezing, itching	0= Absent / None	
		1= Mild: rare bursts, occasional shuffling/ Mild: rare sneezing, occasional sniffing	
		2= Moderate: bursts<10, intermittent rubbing of nose ,and/or eyes or frequent sniffing/ Moderate: sneezing less than 10 times, intermittent rubbing of nose or eyes, frequent sniffing [B]	
		3=Severe: continuous rubbing of nose and/or eyes, periocular swelling and/or long bursts of sneezing, persistent rhinorrhea Severe: continuous rubbing of nose and/or eyes, periocular swelling and/or long bursts of sneezing, persistent rhinorrhea [A].	
	III. Lower respiratory Lower respiratory tract	A. Wheezing Wheezing	0= Absent / None
			1= Mild: expiratory wheezing to auscultation / Mild: expiratory wheezing on auscultation [A].
			2= Moderate: inspiratory and expiratory wheezing [A].
		3= Severe: use of accessory muscles, audible wheezing/ Severe: use of respiratory accessory muscles, wheezing audible without stethoscope [A].	
B. Laryngeal larynx		0= Absent / None	
		1= Mild: >3 discrete episodes of throat clearing or cough, or persistent throat tightness/pain/ Mild: series of 4 or more cough episodes or persistent throat tightness/pain [B].	
	2= Moderate: hoarseness, frequent dry cough / Moderate: hoarseness, frequent dry cough [A].		
IV. Gastrointestinal Gastrointestinal	A. Subjective Complaints Subjective Complaints	3= Severe: stridor / Severe: inspiratory wheezing [A].	
		0= Absent / None	
		1= Mild: complaints of nausea or abdominal pain, itchy mouth/throat/ Mild: nausea, abdominal pain, itchy mouth or throat [B]	
	B. Objective Complaints Objective Symptoms	2= Moderate: frequent complaints of nausea or pain with normal activity/ Moderate: frequent nausea or abdominal pain (no decrease in activity) [B].	
		3= Severe: notably distressed due to GI symptoms with decreased activity/ Severe: suffering significantly from GI symptoms (with decreased activity) [B].	
		0= Absent / None	
1= Mild: 1 episode of emesis or diarrhea / Mild: 1 episode of vomiting or diarrhea [B]			
2= Moderate: 2-3 episodes of emesis or diarrhea or 1 of each / Moderate: 2-3 episodes of emesis or diarrhea or 1 of each [A]			

		3= Severe: >3 episodes of emesis or diarrhea or 2 of each / Severe: more than 3 episodes of emesis or diarrhea or 2 of each [A].
V.		0= Absent: normal heart rate and/or blood pressure for age or patient's baseline Absent: normal heart rate and/or blood pressure for age or patient's baseline
Cardiovascular		1= Mild: subjective response (weak, dizzy), or tachycardia/ Mild: subjective response (weak, dizzy), or tachycardia [B]
Cardiovascular		2= Moderate: drop in blood pressure and/or >20% from baseline, or significant change in mental status Change [A].
Cardiovascular		3= Severe: cardiovascular collapse, signs of impaired circulation (unconsciousness)/ Severe: cardiovascular collapse, signs of impaired circulation (unconsciousness) [A].

(Note: Japanese translation by the Research Secretariat)

5. evaluation item

5.1. Primary outcome

Proportion of sensitization (≥ 0.35 IU) to Jugr1-specific IgE by Immuno CAP method at 24 months of age.

[Rationale].

This study explores the effect of early walnut ingestion on walnut sensitization. In high-risk children with AD, sensitization to walnuts and their 2S-albumin component, Jugr1, often increases from around 18 months of age (Clin Exp Allergy.2024,accepted); Jugr1-specific IgE antibody levels have far superior diagnostic capability than walnut crude antigen-specific IgE¹⁸ . The primary outcome should therefore be the proportion of sensitized (≥ 0.35 IU) Jugr1-specific IgE at 24 months.

5.2 Secondary outcome

1. Proportion of Jug r 1 specific IgE sensitization (≥ 0.35 IU) at 12 months of age
2. Proportion of Jug r 1 specific IgE ≥ 0.70 IU at 12 and 24 months of age
3. Proportion of walnut crude antigen specific IgE sensitization (≥ 0.35 IU) at 12 and 24 months of age
4. Proportion of walnut crude antigen specific IgE ≥ 0.70 IU at 12 and 24 months of age
5. Total IgE and specific IgE values (target antigens: walnut crude antigen, Jug r 1) during study period
6. Proportion of positive determinations in 4g walnut equivalent oral food challenge at visit 6 (volunteers only)
7. Presence/absence of immediate-type walnut allergy history at visit 6 (history-taking)
8. Presence/absence of walnut-induced food protein-induced enterocolitis syndrome at visit 6 (history-taking)
9. Serum TARC values during study period
10. POEM (Patient oriented eczema measure) scores during study period
11. EASI (Eczema Area and Severity Index) scores during study period
12. Caregiver burden regarding trial intervention during study intervention period
13. Presence/absence of expiratory wheeze during study intervention period (history-taking)
14. Presence/absence of allergic rhinitis during study intervention period (history-taking)
15. Adherence to test food consumption
16. Incidence of serious adverse events during study intervention period

[Rationale].

1. 2. 3. 4. → While this study uses Jug r 1 specific sensitization proportion (≥ 0.35 IU) as primary outcome, the cut-off value ≥ 0.7 IU is also exploratively evaluated as secondary

outcome. Similarly, walnut crude antigen proportions $\geq 0.35\text{IU}$ and $\geq 0.7\text{IU}$ are evaluated..

5. For continuous value evaluation including total IgE levels as sensitization indicators.

6. To determine consumption feasibility at typical daily consumption amounts for infants, set at 4g equivalent to 1 walnut. Conducted regardless of Jug r 1 or walnut crude antigen sensitization presence, using 1-3g divided dose considering risk. Made voluntary, as requiring OFC equivalent to 1 walnut at 24 months at the time of recruitment is considered to reduce the feasibility of recruitment.

7. 8.→ Because they are particularly important adverse events during the study intervention period and should be assessed separately in terms of severity and definition.

9.10.11.→To assess the severity and activity of atopic dermatitis during the study intervention period

12.→ To assess the real-life burden of the study intervention content.

13.→ To assess symptom frequency related to bronchial asthma in relation to the development of allergic march

14.→ To assess the prevalence of allergic rhinitis in relation to the development of allergic march.

15.16.→ To assess adherence and safety of the test food

6. Assessment and reporting of adverse events

6.1. Definition of adverse events.

For the purposes of this study, an adverse event is defined as an unfavorable symptom and sign, disease or laboratory abnormality that occurs in a subject during the study intervention period (from the start date of consumption of the test food to the end date of consumption) and is clinically problematic. For specific IgE sensitization to food, inhalant antigens, etc., the name of the disease when accompanied by clinical symptoms is defined as an adverse event; sensitization alone is not included as an adverse event. In addition, a positive OFC test for daily walnut intake in the secondary outcome of visit 6 is not included as an adverse event. The association with the test food is not considered.

6.2. Serious adverse events

Serious adverse events are adverse events corresponding to the following (1)-(6).

(1) Mortalities.

(2) Life-threatening: 'Life-threatening' refers to cases where the study subject is in danger of death at the time of event occurrence, not meaning it might have caused death if more severe.

(3) Requiring hospitalization or prolonged hospitalization for treatment: 'Hospitalization for treatment' refers to cases where a research subject is hospitalized at the research institution, usually for more than one night, because of an adverse event. This includes cases where the subject is admitted for treatment of an adverse event but no specific treatment is performed (bed rest). On the other hand, hospitalization for tests or procedures for the underlying disease or complications that have not worsened from the condition before the administration of the test food, hospitalization for social or convenience purposes not for treatment of the adverse event, and hospitalization for treatment or tests that were planned before the administration of the test food do not constitute 'Hospitalization for treatment'.

(4) Permanent or significant disability/dysfunction .

(5) Congenital anomalies/birth defects

(6) Other medically important conditions or reactions deemed important: Even if not immediately life-threatening or resulting in death or hospitalization, important medical events that could endanger research subjects or require treatment or procedures to prevent the above-

defined outcomes should be considered serious, requiring judgment based on medical and scientific evidence. Anaphylaxis is an example of such events.

6.3. Definition of non-serious adverse events

Non-serious adverse events are all adverse events that do not constitute serious adverse events.

6.4. Severity of adverse events.

The severity of the adverse event is judged on the following three levels

Mild: Discomfort experienced but does not interfere with daily life.

Moderate: Discomfort to the extent that daily life is restricted or affected.

Advanced: Unable to carry out daily activities.

6.5. Adverse event reporting.

The principal investigator and the co-investigator who confirms the occurrence of the adverse event enter the following items into the electronic case report form (eCRF).

- 1) Event name (diagnosis name in principle)
- 2) Onset date
- 3) Severity (mild, moderate and severe)
- 4) Seriousness (serious, non-serious)
- 5) Study intervention measures (continue, suspend, discontinue)
- 6) Treatment (none, yes [if yes, description])
- 7) Outcome (recovered, mildly recovered, not recovered, recovered with sequelae, death, unknown [if the investigation was closed with no recovery or unknown, reason]), date of confirmation of outcome
- 8) Causal relationship with the consumption of the test food (deniable, undeniable [if causal relationship is denied, basis for decision]).

6.6. Reporting of diseases and other illnesses and response to outbreaks of serious diseases

The test food used in this study may cause immediate allergic symptoms (e.g. perioral symptoms, urticaria, redness, cough, wheezing, vomiting, diarrhea, anaphylaxis) and FPIES. However, the amount of protein in the walnut powder used in this study is minute, and it is unlikely that serious illness or other symptoms resulting from it will occur. In the event of serious illnesses, etc., the "Procedures for reporting illnesses, etc." should be followed. If treatment for illnesses caused by the study intervention continues after the study intervention period, the observation period will be extended until the principal investigator or the principal investigator at each site decides that observation is unnecessary from the perspective of ensuring the safety of the subjects.

The term 'illness etc.' refers to illness, disability or death or infection (including abnormal laboratory values and various symptoms) suspected to have resulted from the conduct of the study, i.e. adverse events for which a causal relationship with the study intervention cannot be ruled out. In addition, 'serious illness, etc.' means any of the following among illnesses, etc.

- ① Death
- ② Diseases that may lead to death, etc.
- ③ Admission to a medical institution for treatment^{*} or illness requiring extended hospitalization, etc.

^{*}'Admission to a medical institution for treatment' means when a study subject is admitted to a research institution, usually for more than one night, because of an adverse event. This includes cases where the subject is admitted for treatment of an adverse event, but no specific treatment is performed (bed rest). On the other hand, hospitalization for tests or procedures for the underlying disease or complications that have not worsened from the condition before the administration of the test food, hospitalization for social or convenience purposes not for treatment of the adverse event, and hospitalization for treatment or tests that were planned before the administration of the test food do not constitute 'Hospitalization for treatment'.

- ④ disability
- ⑤ Diseases that may lead to disability

- ⑥ Serious diseases equivalent to ③-⑤ and death and diseases that may lead to death
- ⑦ Congenital diseases or anomalies in later generations

7. Matters relating to statistical analysis.

7.1. Analysis target population

The following data sets will be used for the analysis. Analysis of the primary and secondary outcomes will be performed on the largest analyzed population and, as a reference, on the target population that conforms to the study protocol. Safety outcome item analyses target the safety analysis population. Subjects with serious violations such as consent acquisition violations are excluded from all analysis populations.

(1) Largest analyzed population: Full Analysis Set (FAS)

Population excluding the following subjects from all randomized subjects:

- Subjects who never received study intervention.
- Subjects with no data obtained after study intervention start
- Subjects discovered to violate eligibility criteria post-hoc

(2) Analysis population conforming to the study protocol: Per Protocol Set (PPS)

Population from FAS without the following major protocol deviations:

- Poor adherence (defined as good adherence when $\geq 70\%$ of trial intervention period weeks achieve ≥ 3 times per week investigational food consumption, poor adherence when $< 70\%$).
- Unable to assess adherence
- Consumption of foods containing walnuts other than the test food for more than 7 days during the study period

(3) Safety analysis population: Safety Population (SP)

Population of all subjects who received study intervention at least once.

7.2. Significance Level

Significance level for non-inferiority analysis is one-sided 2.5%. Non-inferiority determination is based on non-inferiority testing and upper limits of two-sided 95% confidence intervals.

Significance level for non-inferiority testing is two-sided 5%, confidence interval confidence coefficient is two-sided 95%.

No multiplicity adjustment is made.

7.3. Analysis methods

For non-inferiority analysis, rate differences and two-sided 95% confidence intervals are calculated. Non-inferiority is determined when the confidence interval upper limit falls below the non-inferiority margin.

One-sided P-values for non-inferiority testing are also calculated.

Other detailed analysis methods are described in the separately defined statistical analysis plan before case fixation.

7.3.1. Summary of background information

Subject background information is summarized by group as follows. For discrete data (gender, caregiver history, etc.), frequencies and percentages (%) for each category are calculated. For continuous data (age in months, height, weight, etc.), mean, standard deviation, median, interquartile range, minimum, and maximum values are calculated.

7.3.2. Analysis of primary outcome

Analysis follows Intention-to-Treat principles. Proportions and 95% confidence intervals for Jug r 1 specific IgE sensitization presence/absence at 24 months are calculated by treatment group. 95% confidence intervals for proportions are calculated using Clopper-Pearson method.

To evaluate the study hypothesis "weaning completion walnut start group (Group B) is non-inferior to early weaning walnut start group (Group A) regarding Jug r 1 specific IgE sensitization prevention effects," between-group differences in Jug r 1 specific IgE sensitization incidence proportions at 24 months and 95% confidence intervals are calculated. Non-inferiority

of weaning completion walnut start group to early weaning walnut start group (Group A) is verified when the confidence interval upper limit falls below the non-inferiority margin. One-sided P-values for non-inferiority testing are calculated using normal approximation.

7.3.3. Analysis of secondary outcomes

Analyses are carried out according to the Intention-to-Treat principle. Details of the analysis methods will be described in a separate statistical analysis plan to be defined prior to case fixation.

7.3.4. Analysis of safety outcomes

Analyses are carried out according to the Intention-to-Treat principle. Details of the analysis methods will be described in a separate statistical analysis plan to be defined prior to case fixation.

7.4. Interim analysis

No interim analysis is carried out.

7.5. Procedure for changing the statistical analysis plan.

Before data fixation, additions and changes to the statistical analysis plan may be made as necessary. If any changes are made to the analysis plan described in the study protocol, the analysis plan and the summary report of the clinical research should also explain the changes and the reasons for the changes.

8. Matters relating to access to original documents and other materials

8.1. Scope of source documents

Source documents in this study are electronic medical records, various laboratory data, questionnaires and diaries.

8.2. Guarantee of direct access to original documents

Principal investigators, co-investigators and the collaborating medical institutes provide and cooperate with direct inspection of all clinical research-related records, including source documents during monitoring, certified clinical research review committees, and regulatory authority investigations related to this study.

9. Quality control and quality assurance matters.

9.1. Monitoring

On-site monitoring will be carried out to ensure that the study is being conducted safely and in accordance with the study protocol and that data is being collected accurately. Monitoring will be carried out by a person nominated by the principal investigator and will be conducted in accordance with the “Monitoring Procedures and Plans”, which will be specified separately.

9.2. audit

No audits are carried out.

10. Ethical considerations.

10.1. Rules and regulations

All personnel involved in this study must thoroughly read, understand and comply with the contents of the of the “World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki” and the “Clinical Research Act”, which all medical research involving human subjects must comply with, before conducting the study. Prior to the commencement of the study, the principal investigator obtains opinions from the certified clinical research review committee on the conduct of the study, receives approval from the administrator of the medical facility where the study is to be conducted, and submits implementation plans to the Minister of Health, Labor and Welfare.

10.2. Handling of personal data.

Those involved in the conduct of the study will give sufficient consideration to the privacy of the subjects and the protection of their personal information. Although the date of birth will be collected at EDC as necessary information at the time of enrolment, the principal investigator will put in place the necessary safeguards and systems for the protection of personal data in the conduct of the study. Individuals will not be identified in the final fixed data.

Principal investigators will give subjects a subject identification number unique to the study and manage data and samples in such a way that individuals cannot be identified. The subject identification number will be used to identify individuals in the research office. Subject identification numbers and patient IDs will be appropriately managed by the personal information manager, defined at each collaborating medical facilities using the list of study subjects and will not be communicated to the statistical analysis manager. Confidentiality agreements exist with B-Case Co. under joint research contracts.

Personal information identifying subjects is not used when publishing study results. Personnel involved in the conduct of this study do not leak subject privacy information obtained through source document inspection to third parties. When using subject data and specimens obtained in this study for purposes other than this study, separate consent is obtained from subjects' legal representatives as necessary. When using subject data and specimens obtained in this study for future research, separate study protocols are created for new certified clinical research review committee or ethics committee approval applications before appropriate use.

*Note: In study-related materials distributed to subjects, legal representatives, and caregivers, subject identification numbers are described as study IDs.

10.3. Provision of samples and information to other institutions

The study is a multicenter study and the samples and information collected will be used jointly according to 4.6. Observational and laboratory items and treatment information to be reported.

10.4. Benefits, burdens and measures to minimize anticipated risks to subjects.

The benefit to subjects in this study, regardless of which group they are allocated to, is that consumption of the test food from the weaning period may reduce sensitization to walnuts. In addition, if desired, OFC will be performed on the common daily walnut intake for infants at the final visit, so that the presence of immediate-type symptoms can be confirmed under physician observation in medical institutions. Disadvantages include the time and effort required to have subjects consume the test food at least three times a week during the intervention period, and the burden on the subjects' legal representatives to fill in the diary and questionnaires. In addition, allergic symptoms may occur due to the intake of the test food. Given these risks, the initial intake and the first intake at the time of the dose escalation will be carried out at each collaborating medical institute. However, given the minute amount of protein in test food used in this trial, the occurrence of serious diseases resulting from it is unlikely. When serious diseases with undeniable causal relationships to walnuts occur in study subjects, principal investigators, and co-investigators promptly discontinue study intervention, take necessary measures such as treatment, and strive to ensure the safety of the subject and provide the best possible treatment.

11. Handling and storage of records.

11.1. Handling and storage of materials

The collaborating medical facilities in this study will appropriately store the following documents relating to the conduct of the study, as specified by the principal investigator and each medical facility according to each collaborating medical facility's regulations. Storage period is the longer of either the period determined by each medical facility or 5 years from study completion date. Thereafter, documents are disposed of in states where individuals cannot be identified.

- 1) Study protocols, study plans, documents pertaining to the explanation to the subjects of specified clinical trial and their consent, summary reports and other documents or copies thereof prepared by the principal investigator pursuant to the Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare Ordinance under Article 12 of the Act.
- 2) Documents related to certified clinical research review committee review opinion services.
- 3) Documentation on monitoring (monitoring sites only)
- 4) Source documents, etc.
- 5) Contract for the conduct of specified clinical trial (principal investigators only)

- 6) Documents containing an overview of medicines and other products used in specified clinical trial and records relating to medicines and other products.
- 7) Other documents necessary to carry out specified clinical trial.

11.2. Storage of samples, etc. and use of samples, etc. by other institutions.

The principal investigator will properly store the subject's samples and other materials obtained in the study for a period of at least five years from the date of study completion. Residual blood (serum) from specimens examined at NCCHD testing centers will be frozen and stored at the Allergy Center sample storage center. All specimens from subjects at other institutions are disposed by appropriate means. If residual samples are to be used for future research that is not identified at the time consent is received, separate research subject explanation and consent are obtained before use.

11.3. Data collection methods

Study-related data is collected via Electronic Case Report Forms (eCRF) using the NCCHD REDCap system in formats not including personally identifiable information. Responsible physicians and co-investigators at each collaborating medical facility enter data into eCRF after each visit completion. Subjects' legal representatives record in diaries.

12. Financial payments and compensation for the conduct of clinical research.

12.1. Funding sources and financial relationships (conflicts of interest, COI).

The study will be funded by the Research and Development Fund for Growth and Development (2023B-14) and will also be conducted as a collaborative study using test foods provided by B-Case Co., Ltd. B-Case Co., Ltd. will be involved in part of the conduct of the study (provision of test food and delivery to subjects), but not in the analysis of the study results. The state of COI due to joint research will not affect the planning and conduct of the study, the results and interpretation of the study, and the conduct of the study will not harm the rights and interests of the study subjects. Regarding the management of COI with the company concerned, the principal investigator has submitted a COI management standard and management plan to certified clinical research review committee for approval, in accordance with the guidance on COI management for clinical research in the "Clinical Research Act". Each researcher appropriately manages COI related to this study in accordance with the COI management standards and management plan, and disclose them appropriately upon request of the academic societies and medical journals where the study results are scheduled to be published.

12.2. Research-related costs

The test food in the study was provided by B-Case Co., Ltd., and the tests (blood tests for IgE antibodies, etc.) and drug prescriptions are conducted within normal insurance practice coverage, paid through subject's health insurance or self-payment.

To reduce burdens associated with clinical research participation, Quo cards worth 2,000 yen per visit are provided to subjects as participation cooperation fees.

12.3. Health damage compensation

When health damage occurs due to this trial, treatment is provided using subjects' health insurance with best efforts as in normal medical care. For this trial, clinical research insurance is purchased with the principal investigator, co-investigators, and all personnel involved in this trial as insured parties to prepare for compensation for health damage occurring to subjects. This insurance pays insurance money for damages incurred when insured parties bear compensation responsibility or legal liability when health damage (death or grade 1 or 2 sequelae according to drug adverse reaction damage relief system standards) occurs to subjects due to clinical research.

13. Publication of information on clinical research.

The study will be registered in the database (jRCT: Japan Registry of Clinical Trials) maintained by the Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare (MHLW) prior to the start of the study. Study results belong to the NCCHD. The main study results will be submitted to academic journals after the final analysis is completed. In principle, the first author of the main article of the study results will be determined by the research office. Co-authors will be determined by the

principal investigator in accordance with the Uniform Requirements for Manuscripts Submitted to Biomedical Journals of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors. All co-authors should review the content of the article prior to submission and agree on the content of the publication. Any researcher who disagrees with the content will be discussed and, if agreement is still not reached, the study office may choose not to include that researcher as a co-author.

14. Duration of clinical research.

Subject registration period: From the date of publication of the clinical study in the jRCT until 30 September 2026.

Total study period: From the date of publication of the clinical study in the jRCT to 30 November 2029.

If the implementation period is extended for reasons such as not reaching the target number of cases within the research implementation period, the extension is subject to approval by certified clinical research review committee.

15. Matters relating to the explanation of and consent to study subjects.

15.1. Preparation and revision of informed consent documents and consent forms

Informed consent documents and consent forms are prepared by the principal investigator and used after approval by certified clinical research review committee. If revisions are made, they are reapplied to the certified research review committee and used after approval is obtained. The principal investigator will promptly revise the informed consent documents when information is obtained that may influence the subjects' legal representatives' intention to continue participating in the research.

15.2. Informed consent

The study will be conducted after review and approval by the certified clinical research review committee and publication in the jRCT. Prior to the commencement of the study, the principal investigator and co-investigators provide clear explanations to candidate legal representatives based on informed consent documents including all items below according to the Clinical Research Act, obtaining written consent for trial participation based on legal representatives' free will after achieving sufficient understanding.

When obtaining consent, sufficient time and opportunity for questions are provided to legal representatives' to enable them to decide whether or not to participate in the study, along with sufficient answers to questions. If consent is obtained, the subjects' legal representatives' and the principal investigator or co-investigator should sign and date the consent form. A copy of the consent form and the informed consent documents should be given to the patient (subject), while the original consent form should be kept at the collaborating medical facilities. Explanation includes that consent can be withdrawn at any time even after initially given, and that no disadvantages result from consent withdrawal.

Principal investigators and co-investigators promptly explain to legal representatives and confirm study continuation intentions when new important information regarding walnut powder safety is obtained or when important information that may affect subjects' legal representatives' consent intentions is obtained. Principal investigators or co-investigators record explanation dates, explainers, explanation content, continuation intentions, and confirmation dates in medical records.

[Explanatory Items]

- ① Study name, approval by collaborating medical institution and study plan has been submitted to the Minister of Health, Labor and Welfare.
- ② Name of the implementing medical institution and name and title of the principal investigator.
- ③ Reasons for selection as a subject for this study.
- ④ Benefits and disadvantages of the study.
- ⑤ Study participation refusal is voluntary.
- ⑥ Withdrawal of consent.

- ⑦ No treatment disadvantage by participation refusal or consent withdrawal.
- ⑧ Study information publication methods.
- ⑨ Availability of research protocols and other research implementation materials upon request by research subjects or legal representatives and acquisition or inspection methods
- ⑩ Protection of personal data of subjects of this study.
- ⑪ Specimen storage and disposal methods.
- ⑫ Conflicts of interest including funding from pharmaceutical manufacturers and other compensation.
- ⑬ System for responding to complaints and enquiries.
- ⑭ Costs related to the conduct of this research.
- ⑮ Availability and content of other treatments and comparison with the expected benefits and disadvantages of other treatments.
- ⑯ Compensation and provision of medical care for health damage caused by the conduct of this study.
- ⑰ Review matters at the certified clinical research review committee that performs review opinion duties for this study and other matters relating to the certified clinical research review committee for this study.

15.3. Informed assent

Since trial subjects are infants, informed assent is not conducted.

15.4. In case of consent withdrawal.

If the subjects' legal representatives request consent withdrawal, this will be handled in accordance with the following.

The study investigator at each site, reports to the principal investigator, and confirms the withdrawal of consent to participate in the study by the subject's legal representative using a withdrawal of consent form. Consent withdrawal includes participation consent withdrawal (withdrawing participation only while not deleting data up to withdrawal for analysis use) and complete consent withdrawal (withdrawing research participation and data use). Either withdrawal type results in deletion of personal information (names, addresses) stored at each implementing medical facility at withdrawal.

In the event of withdrawal of consent to participate, the principal investigator (or co-investigator) at each site asks the research office to withdraw consent to participate in the study and dispose any remaining samples. The research office will request the sample storage center to dispose residual blood (serum) in the sample storage center.

In the case of complete withdrawal of consent, the principal investigator (or co-investigator) at each site will ask the research office to withdraw consent to participate in the study and dispose any relevant data. The research office asks the sample storage center to dispose the relevant subject's data and samples, the data management officer excludes the withdrawn subject's data from the analysis data set and the sample storage center dispose residual blood (serum).

15.5. Reporting to the Clinical Research Review Committee, the Minister of Health, Labor and Welfare and the administrator of the implementing medical facility.

15.5.1. Regular report

Principal and co-investigators conduct regular reports to clinical research review committees within 2 months after each 1-year period completion from implementation plan submission to the Minister of Health, Labour and Welfare (regional bureau), after reporting to implementing medical institution managers. After reporting to the Clinical Research Review Committee, the principal investigator provides information to each principal investigator, who reports the content of the information provided by the principal investigator to the administrator of the implementing medical institution.

Additionally, principal investigators submit regular reports to the Minister of Health, Labour and Welfare (regional bureau) within 1 month of receiving clinical research review committee opinions.

15.5.2. Non-conformity Reporting

When research non-compliance with regulations, study protocols, or procedures, or research data falsification or fabrication becomes apparent, co-investigators who become aware report to responsible physicians, who report to administrators of implementing medical institutions and principal investigators. Principal investigators provide information to all responsible physicians. When principal investigators determine serious non-compliance, they promptly seek clinical research review committee opinions.

Among non-compliance, instances of not following study protocols due to urgent danger avoidance for subjects or other medically unavoidable reasons are not included in serious non-compliance.

The following cases are determined as serious non-compliance:

- Serious eligibility/exclusion criteria violations
- Discontinuation criteria violations that may threaten subject safety
- Data fabrication or falsification
- Subject registration without consent (including consent form loss)
- Other instances deemed serious by principal investigators

15.5.3. Report from the audit officer.

No audits are planned.

15.6. Changes to the study protocol

When the content of the study protocol is changed, the principal investigator reports to the administrator of the implementing medical facility and submits a notification of changes (Form 2), the revised implementation plan (jRCT) and the notification of the approved clinical research review committee to the Minister of Health, Labor and Welfare. The principal investigator provides information on any changes to the study protocol to the principal investigators at each site. The principal investigator reports the content of the information provided to the administrator of the site.

15.6.1. Amendments to the study protocol

- 1) May increase the risk to patients participating in the study.
- 2) Substantial impact on the study's primary outcome.
- 3) Essential impact on the system for conducting the study.

A partial change to a study protocol that corresponds to one or more of the above is defined as an amendment. Version number upgrades of the study protocol and the informed consent documents due to revisions are indicated at the rank of 1, such as 2.0, 3.0, 4.0.... After the changes to the study protocol are approved by the certified clinical research review committee, the principal investigator submits a notification of changes to the implementation plan to the regional health bureau and also indicates the date of the certified clinical research review committee's approval on the cover page of the study protocol. After approval by the certified clinical research review committee, permission is obtained from the administrator of the implementing medical facility regarding the details of the amendment. If approval is granted, the principal investigator sends a copy of the approval letter to the research office and the changes to the study protocol take effect (the principal investigator decides whether to suspend patient enrolment during this period). The research office will announce the actual effective date, and after the effective date, the study will be conducted in accordance with the changes approved by the certified clinical research review committee. Until the effective date, the intervention and evaluation of enrolled patients will be conducted according to the version of the study protocol before the amendment, but if the safety of the subjects is threatened by the content of the study protocol before the change, such as inadequate criteria for changing the intervention, deviations from the study protocol to enhance the safety of the subjects during the intervention will be permitted.

15.6.2. Revisions of study protocol.

- 1) Do not increase the risk to study participants.

- 2) No substantial effect on the study's primary outcome.
- 3) Do not essentially affect the conduct of the study.

Changes to a study protocol that meet all of the above are defined as revisions. Including changes due to typographical errors or facility-specific information changes, study protocol changes not involving study protocol changes regarding facility-specific information, and conflict of interest changes. Patient registration will not be temporarily suspended in the event of a revision. Version numbers of the study protocol and the informed consent document due to revisions are shown to one decimal place, e.g. 1.1, 1.2, 1.3.... When the changes to the study protocol are approved by the certified clinical research review committee, a notification of changes to the implementation plan is submitted to the regional health authorities and the date of approval by the certified clinical research review committee is noted on the cover page of the study protocol. The effective date of the changes to the study protocol are after the jRCT publication and the facility manager's approval. The effective date is the date after the submission of the notification of changes to the implementation plan to the regional health authorities. The actual effective date will be announced by the research office and the study will be conducted after the effective date in accordance with the revised content approved by the certified clinical research review committee. If the changes affect the format of the electronic case report form (eCRF), the principal investigator will request the data management officer to change the format.

15.6.3. Subject explanation and re-consent for study protocol changes

When study protocols are changed, principal investigators correspondingly change subject informed consent documents. When certified clinical research review committees provide opinions that written subject explanation and re-consent are necessary, written consent is obtained again.

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15.8. appendix

- 1) Attachment 1: Response flow for the appearance of allergic symptoms due to ingestion of test foods
- 2) Exhibit 2: Diagnostic Definition of Food Protein-Induced Gastroenteropathy
- 3) List of Research Physicians
- 4) Procedures for Reporting Diseases, etc.
- 5) Monitoring Procedures and Plans
- 6) Logbook_WISH-J
- 7) Requirements for Implementing Medical Institutions

*In addition, specifications and notes for 1) and 6), which are materials for participants in the Appendix, may be adjusted as appropriate during operation in consideration of ease of understanding, etc.